

Study on formation of intermetallic compound layer during aluminium to steel dissimilar joining: A Review

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Abstract

Use of lightweight metals in automobile industry is viable approach to enhance fuel efficiency and reduce CO₂ and unhealthy gas emissions. Automotive manufacturers focused on reducing weight of vehicle and aluminum especially used as best alternative to steel for car body structure. It is not possible to replace steel by Aluminum completely due to safety and strength constraints of the automotives. Joining of Aluminum to steel face difficulty due to their incompatible thermophysical characteristics. At the aluminium to steel brazing interface, formation of brittle intermetallic compound layer composed with Al rich phases on Al side like FeAl₃, Fe₂Al₅ and Fe rich phases on steel side Fe₃Al, Fe₃Al₂ etc. Al rich phases FeAl₃, Fe₂Al₅ shows needle like structure. MIG weld brazing and CMT using Al Si base filler wire offers good fluidity and less crack sensitivity attributed to formation of ternary phases Al-Fe-Si ductile in nature. Al-Mg-Si alloys (6XXX series) and Al-Mg alloys (5XXX series) has found to be excellent base metal, Mg helps to improve strength and Si helps to enhance fluidity. Galvanized coated steel gives better results than uncoated steel because of Zinc from steel surface responsible for enhance fluidity. This assessment focused on the key challenges during Al to steel dissimilar joining by arc welding processes. Influence of welding parameter like welding current, speed, wire feed speed, CTWD, presetting gap, pre and post weld heat treatment and filler wire composition like Al-Mg, Al-Si5, Al-Si12 etc. Their influence on mechanical and microstructural property of weld joint.

Keywords: Automotive metals, dissimilar joints, arc welding process, intermetallic layer, microstructure, mechanical property.

1. Introduction

The main material used for manufacturing cars and components along with future trends are steel, Aluminum, Magnesium, copper, Plastic and carbon fiber[1, 2]. The main features of selecting these materials having various properties like high strength, ability to absorb impact energy when collision, good machinability, corrosion resistance. The material especially for the automobile bodies is numerous applications and includes thermal, chemical and mechanical resistance easy manufacturing and durability.

Steel has been primary material used in automotive industries since the 1920s. Steel used in the automotive industry possess excellent formability, machinability, weldability, absorb impact energy, Strength and most affordable material [1, 3, 4]. Therefore, it retains crash safety and comfort to occupants. It is versatile material used in vehicle body, transmission components and chassis, can be called backbone of entire vehicle. It also provides corrosion resistance with zinc coating[5].

Aluminum and aluminum alloy having excellent combination of light weight, high strength, great corrosion resistance and reasonable cost so that automotive manufacturers given preference in car body [6]. Aluminum alloys density is 2.7 kg m^{-3} which is about one-third of the density of iron 7.8 kg m^{-3} .

In order to meet the demand for lighter and more fuel efficient vehicles a significant effort is currently being directed toward the substitution of aluminum for steel in the body structure. Due to their properties like high specific strength, ductility, good formability and good corrosion resistance[7, 8]. Miklos Tisza et al [9]reveals that joining of multi-material (Al to Steel) is helpful to reduce weight of vehicle. The usage of aluminum body in white exceeds the cost however the fuel saving benefits were more due to reduction in mass vehicle.

Automakers are showing interest in hybrid structures between aluminum to coated steel for weight reduction and energy saving which has a high technical economic and environmental potential. Steel cannot be eliminated completely from the vehicle structures due to safety reasons (Crash performance) and it also gives better mechanical properties to fulfill strength requirement and easily available[10-12].Joining of Al-steel is difficult task due to their different physical properties and thermal properties like melting point, thermal conductivity. Difficulties encountered during fusion welding of aluminium to steel such as spatter, poor weld metallurgical compatibility, incomplete fusion, formation of Al rich hard and brittle IMC layer.

In previous work various welding methods have been used to produce dissimilar joint such as Resistance spot welding (RSW), Laser welding/brazing[13-15], Metal inert gas welding/brazing (MIGW or MIGB)[12, 16-20], Tungsten inert gas welding/brazing (TIGW or TIGB)[11, 21-26] produces more heat input and spatter, Cold metal transfer process(CMT)[17, 27]. From previous scenario, MIG brazing offers good opportunity in dissimilar metal joining (Al to Steel)[12, 17, 28]. Al to steel joining is possible by CMT low heat input process [12, 27, 29-36]. CMT brazing low heat input process ensures controlled IMC layer formation which distinguishes CMT process from conventional GMA brazing[37-39].

This review mainly focused on growth of intermetallic layer during Aluminium to steels dissimilar joining using arc welding such as Laser welding/brazing, Metal inert gas welding/brazing, Tungsten inert gas welding/brazing (TIGW or TIGB) produces more heat input and spatter, Cold metal transfer process(CMT). We also discuss the process of formation of IMC layer and its behavior, microstructural

analysis of joint. Also discussed effect of heat input and process parameter on intermetallic compound formation.

2. Growth of Intermetallic compound layer

Some researchers have looked into aluminium alloys from the 5000 and 6000 series, which are primarily alloyed with magnesium and silicon, respectively. Aluminum alloys of the 5000 and 6000 series contain trace quantities of additional elements, depending on the grade of aluminium. These additional elements were responsible for the formation of other IMC compounds during dissimilar Al to steel welding-brazing joint. Welding takes place between aluminium alloy and filler metal, whereas brazing takes place between filler metal and steel sheet. At the filler wire to steel (brazing) interface, a brittle reaction layer was introduced.

Fundamentals of Growth Kinetics

Phase transformation can occur during molten liquid solidification, although it eventually happens to reduce the total Gibbs free energy of a system. This study is only focused on diffusional transformations, which require the mass movement of a solute atom inside a matrix to form a new phase. Diffusion, or the movement of a solute atom inside a matrix due to a chemical potential gradient, is the primary process for mass atomic movement in metallic systems. The rate of diffusion increases with temperature. Diffusional transformations are often distinguished by two distinct stages such as nucleation and coarsening or subsequent growth of that phase. Nucleation occurs readily in metal to metal couples with sufficiently high temperatures and the phase becomes stable once a critical nucleus size is attained.

Growth is caused by the nuclei coarsening and the volume of the newly formed phases rising. Growth in diffusional processes is regulated in two ways such as interfacial controlled growth and diffusion-controlled growth. To differing degrees, both interface controlled growth and diffusion controlled growth are time and temperature dependent [40]. Interfacial growth is also known as reaction-controlled growth. In this growth mechanism, the formation reaction of the phase inhibits the growth and diffusion across the newly formed phase occurs readily. The reaction of phase formation happens rapidly in diffusion controlled growth, but the formation is restricted by the rate at which one or more components may diffuse to sustain growth [41]. In interfacial controlled growth, layer thickness is directly proportional to the duration of time for a given temperature.

The governing equation for Interfacial Controlled Flux relationship,

$$\frac{J}{C} = v = \text{Constant} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where, J as atomic flux, C as solute concentration and v as interfacial velocity.

Equation can be simplified in 1-D into,

$$\Delta x = K_{\beta}^{eff} t$$

Where, Δx is the change in layer thickness, K_{β}^{eff} is the interfacial controlled growth coefficient controlled by the activation energy for a solute atom to jump across the interface and is a function of temperature and t is time.

In interfacial control growth the rate at which the interface grows does not change as a function of time.

Interfacial (Reaction) Controlled Growth Equation,

$$x = K_{\beta}^{eff} t \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

Diffusion regulated growth is characterized by lowering growth rate as layer thickness rises rather than constant interfacial velocities. Equation 3 shows the relationship with atomic flux in this situation, where J is flux, C is concentration, x is layer thickness and D is diffusion coefficient[42]. In this case, the layer thickness is proportional to the square root of time. This growth in one dimension can be described by Equation 4, where x is the intermetallic layer thickness, k is a material dependent growth constant and t is time. The equation can be simplified to Equation 5 which assumes $\Delta x=0$ when $t=0$. k can be calculated using Equation 6, where k is the pre-exponential factor, Q is the activation enthalpy and T is the temperature.

Diffusion Controlled Flux Relationship [42]

$$\frac{J}{\frac{-\delta C}{\delta x}} = D = \text{constant} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

Parabolic Growth Equation

$$\frac{d\Delta x}{dt} = \frac{k}{\Delta x} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Simplified Diffusion Controlled Growth equation,

$$(\Delta x)^2 = 2kt \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

Parabolic Growth Coefficient Calculation,

$$k = k_0 e^{(-Q/kRT)} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

The formation of intermetallic compounds at the Al to steel brazing interface has been essential phenomenon to hold acceptable joint strength. Many researchers have concentrated on it. These investigations given the morphology of Al to steel interface ranging from a layer of 2.5 μm in thick layer for arc welding[39]. After lengthy heat treatments, the IMC layers exceeded a millimeter in thickness [43]. After investigations many IMC compounds have been reported such as FeAl_3 , Fe_2Al_5 , FeAl_2 , FeAl and Fe_3Al [44, 45] however these phases are not limited to the equilibrium phases described in the Al-Fe phase diagram. D Naoi et al[46] reported that, the Fe_2Al_5 compound is formed initially by reaction diffusion of

aluminum into steel substrate and then additional Fe–Al intermetallic compounds are synthesized during subsequent heating process. The growth of Fe_2Al_5 phase is governed by volume diffusion. Formation of Fe_2Al_5 and $FeAl_3$ should be decreased through heat input reduction. S. Kobayashi et al[47] indicated that coating layers of hot dip aluminized steel were primarily composed of $FeAl$ and Fe_2Al_5 phases and the thickness of the coating layer increased with increasing immersion temperature (973–1173K). When temperatures exceeded 1273K during the subsequent diffusion treatment process, $FeAl$ and Fe_3Al phases were found. According to Arrhenius' law, the thickness of the Fe_2Al_5 phase is affected by both temperature and time. As a result, in order to improve mechanical properties and minimize brittleness in the Fe–Al joint produced by MIG brazing.

Table 1: Filler metal, IMCs, IMC layer thickness and fracture location of steel and aluminum welding.

Sr no	Welding Process	Materials	Filler metals	IMC layer thickness (μm)	Intermetallic	Fracture zone	Reference
1	MIG welding/ Brazing	Al 2B50 1.0mm/ 1Cr18Ni9Ti	ER4043	10	Al86Fe14 Al0.7 Fe3Si0.3	Interface failure	[48]
		5052 Al alloy/ GI steel	ER4043	1.25-3.05	FeAl3 Fe2Al5 Fe2Al5Zn0.4	HAZ of Al	[49]
		Al 1060 1.0 mm/ Hot-dip GI steel 1.0 mm	Al-Si	10	Fe2Al5 FeAl2 FeAl3	HAZ of Al	[50]
		Al6061-T6 / IF steel	ER4043	1.6-4	Fe2Al5 FeAl3	Interface failure	[51]
		Carbon steel (SPCC)/ A1050P-H24	BA4047W	2.5	α -Al matrix, Al-Si eutectic, Al-Fe-Si, Al5Fe2, Al3Fe Al7.4Fe2Si Al3Fe	HAZ of Al	[12]
		6K21 Al 1.6 mm/ SPRC440 1.4 mm	ER4043	3.2	FeAl3, Fe2Al5	HAZ of Al	[52]
2	TIG Welding / brazing	Al 5A06 3.0 mm/ SUS321 austenite stainless 3.0 mm	ER4047	20-35(top) 12(corner) <5(middle)	Al7.2Fe2Si Fe2Al5 FeSi2	Welded seam and steel interface	[53]
3	Laser welding	Al 6016 T4 1.2 mm/ low carbon DP600 steel 0.77 mm	Zn-15%Al	3-23	48% Al, 31% Fe 21% Zn	Welded seam and steel interface	[54]
4	Cold Metal Transfer process	Al 6061-T6 2.0mm/ zinc coated low-carbon steel 1.2mm	ER4043 (AlSi5%)	-	-	HAZ close to weld	[55]

		AC 170 PX Al alloy/ ST06 Z GI steel	ER4043 ER4047	1.50-2.03	$\text{FeAl}_9\text{Si}_3+\alpha\text{-Al}$, FeAl_3 , Fe_2Al_5	-	[56]
		AA6061T6 1.0mm/ GI mild steel 1.0mm	ER4043 (AlSi5%)	-	Fe_3Al , FeAl_2 FeAl_3 , Fe_2Al_5	-	[57]
5	Resistance spot Welding	A5052 1.5 mm/ DP 600 1.2 mm	-	3.3 (Fe_2Al_5) 0.67-15.8 ($\text{Fe}_4\text{Al}_{13}$)	$\text{Fe}_4\text{Al}_{13}$ Fe_2Al_5	Elongated dimple and cleavage	[58]
		EN AW 6008-T66 Al 1.5 mm/ GI HSS 1.0 mm	-	5 (lathlike) 2.5-8 (needle-like)	Fe_2Al_5 $\text{Fe}_4\text{Al}_{13}$	Interfacial layer	[59]

In CMT weld brazing joining of Al to coated steel molten filler wire deposited on steel surface. Wavy edges were discovered as a result of the unpredictable nature of Zn vapor concerns such as porosity. When the Zn vapor unable to escape from the weld area, it affects the arc and liquid droplet of filler metal and causing arc instability due to this molten droplet deviated which led to formation of wavy edges[55].

Figure 1: Schematic representation of formation of wavy mechanism during gas metal arc Welding-brazing:(a) macroscopic view of welding process (b) formation of waves (magnified dashed rectangle in (a)), (c) growth of Fe_2Al_5 (magnified dashed rectangle in (b)), (d) the formation of void and (e) the final morphology of void[60].

3. Effect of process parameter on IMC layer

M. Potesser et al [61] observed the formation of FeAl_3 , Fe_3Al and Fe_2Al_5 intermetallic compounds during CMT weld brazing of 1.5 mm AW 5182 and 1 mm Zinc coated steel sheets in lap joint configuration using ER4043 and SSAISiMn filler wire. The thickness of intermetallic phase is $5.1\mu\text{m}$ and $3.47\mu\text{m}$ when using SSAISiMn and ER4043 (AlSi5) filler wire attributed to lower Si content. Fe_2Al_5 and Fe_2Al have a higher hardness by 10-15% than FeAl_3 , and they are ductile in nature.

Hong Ma et al[60] has joined thin 1mm 5052 Al alloy and hot dipped GI steel by gas metal arc fusion welding. They investigated the morphology of weld joints by altering the welding current.

Figure 1 shows that when the welding current increases from 45A to 75A, also increase in IMC layer thickness. They observed needle like structure (layer I) in Al side due to sinter diffusion of Fe in Al and observed plate like structure (layer II) composed with Fe_2Al_5 in steel side. Wavy nature was detected in IMC layer II from the steel side as shown in Figure 2(a, b, c) by the dashed ellipse. Welding current increases waves also increases, which are symmetric but grow in size with the same welding current because the peak temperature of interface nearly reaches the melting point of steel. However, with 75A welding current voids are formed between IMC layer and waves shown in Figure 2(C, d) due to the formation of Fe_2Al_5 .

Figure 2: Microstructure of brazed interface in the central zone at different welding currents: (a) 55 A, (b) 65 A, (c) 75 A and (d) magnified zone in (c)[60].

Dissimilar Al to steel joining has produces welding-brazing joint. Welding takes place between aluminium alloy and filler metal, whereas brazing takes place between filler metal and steel sheet. At the file wire to steel (brazing) interface, a brittle reaction layer was introduced. It consists of Fe_xAl_y binary compounds, which aid to hold the joint and increase mechanical properties like tensile strength. The growth of intermetallic compound (IMC) layer depends on chemical composition of filler metal and base metal and also depends on diffusivity of Fe and Al due to change heat input. These compounds are Al rich FeAl_3 , FeAl_5 etc. provides brittleness in the layer.

Figure 3: (a and b) IMC layer made with Al–5Si filler wire, c) IMC layer made with Al–12Si filler wire[62].

The size of IMC layer is not uniform Al_5Fe_2 and Al_3Fe are thinner at extremes and growing slightly near the center. Formation of IMC layer suffers from 1) Partial fusion of Al 2) wetting surface of steel 3) Dissolution of steel in molten Al 4) Atom diffusion FeAl in steel 5) Formation of Fe_2Al_5 [44]. The Al rich intermetallic compounds FeAl_2 , Fe_2Al_5 and FeAl_3 etc. which is brittle nature whereas Fe rich intermetallic compound Fe_3Al , FeAl which gives good oxidation resistance and wear resistance [17, 36].

Y. Su et.al [63] investigated joint strength of 5052Al alloy and galvanized mild steel using various filler wires such as Al, AlSi_5 , AlSi_{12} and $\text{AlMg}_{4.5}$. It was found that the thickness of interface layer is more produces weak joint in $\text{AlMg}_{4.5}$ compared to Al-Si filler wire.

Table 2 : Properties of several intermetallic compounds Fe_xAl_y [64, 65].

Phase	Al content /at%	Structure	Microhardness, (HV)	Density ($\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$)
Fe_3Al	25	BCC	250-350	6.67
FeAl	30	BCC	400-520	5.37
Fe_2Al_7	63	BCC	650-680	–
FeAl_2	66-67	Rhombohedral	1000-1050	4.36
Fe_2Al_5	69.7-73.2	Orthorhombic	1000-1100	4.11
FeAl_3	74-76	Monoclinic	820-980	3.95

Table 2 displays crystal structure, hardness value and density of phases formed during Fe-Al diffusion process during dissimilar Al to steel joining. It was observed that the hardness of the Fe-Al intermetallic compounds was much greater than base metals confirms brittle IMC layer.

IMC layer thickness measured by

Zahra s. et al[23] worked on joining of ENAW-6014 T4 to GI mild steel DC04 by CMT in butt joint configuration. They also developed numerical model based on the temperature of field available at interface. The peak temperature of the thermal cycle is around 800°C, which has a direct impact on the thickness of the IMC layer.

The total thickness of IMC layer,

$$X_{IM} = \sum_{i=1}^m \Delta x_{IM,i}$$

$$\Delta x_{IM,i} = \sqrt{\frac{k_i}{4t_i} \Delta t_i}$$

Where

$\Delta x_{IM,i}$ = Growth increment

t_i =actual time of growth

Δt_i = time increment

k_i = Coefficient Growth rate

$$k_i = K_0 \exp\left(-\frac{Q}{RT_i}\right)$$

The formation mechanism IMC layer is determined by the thermal cycle, diffusion period and of filler and base metal composition. Thermal cycle is used to predict the formation of intermetallic compounds and the kinetics at the brazing interface. Figure 4 shows thermal cycle with three different heat inputs ranging from 155 to 235 Jmm⁻¹ with rise in temperature from 985 to 1301K, resulting in the formation of intermetallic compounds such as FeAl₃, Fe₃Al, Fe₂Al₅ etc.

Figure 4: The thermal cycle (temperature-time history) of the joint region[17].

Diffusion/Calculation

The diffusivity of Al in Fe is,

$$D_{Al}^{Fe} = 2.5 \times 10^{-14} \exp\left(-\frac{3058}{RT}\right) \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$$

Where, T is Temperature, K and R universal gas constant.

The ratio of width of interface,

$$\left(\frac{X_1}{X_2}\right)_{Al} = \sqrt{(D_{Al}^{Fe}) \frac{t_1}{t_2}}$$

Growth of FeAl_3 was assumed to be controlled due to diffusion and Fe_3Al has been observed in reaction layer with higher stability. It gives better agreement in experiment Al to Fe diffusivity [17, 66]. FeAl_3 thermodynamically highly stable as compared to Fe_3Al , Fe_2Al_5 etc.

4. Effect of heat input on IMC layer

The thickness of the intermetallic compound layer is affected indirectly by the weld heat input. Figure 5 shows variation of compound layer thickness and shear tensile strength with heat input. Weld heat input increases 100 Jmm^{-1} to 380 Jmm^{-1} , also increasing IMC layer thickness due to the erosion phenomenon of Fe atom dissolving into liquid Al, as well as an increase in cooling cycle attributed to increased diffusion time. IMC thickness governs joint strength [67]. The failure of the joint from interface is caused by a high or excessive thickness of the IMC layer or compound layer. During the solidification of the weld pool FeAl , Fe_3Al , Fe_2Al_5 and FeAl_3 compounds formed in IMC layer. The strength of weld joint initially increases up to 250 Jmm^{-1} then decreases with increase in thickness of the IMC layer due to higher primary dendrite arm spacing.

Figure 5: FESEM images at different weld heat input (a) 100Jmm⁻¹ (b) 250J mm⁻¹ and (c) 380Jmm⁻¹ (d) Enlarged image of the rectangle in (c). (e) Effect of heat input on reaction layer thickness (f) Effect of heat input on shear tensile strength[67].

Jin yang et al[68] investigated the effect of heat input on an IMC layer made of AA5754 aluminium alloy and Q235 low carbon steel using CMT. Weld metal or fusion zone has low interfacial energy and high interfacial bonding. At low heat input upto 157Jmm⁻¹, In a single plate phase reaction layer or IMC layer contains Al_{7.2}Fe_{1.8}Si at fusion zone or interface. When the heat input exceeds 201Jmm⁻¹, the compound of the IMC layer changes from FE Al₃Si to Al_{7.2}Fe_{1.8}Si. The fracture location is also dependent on heat input at low heat input fails from the fusion zone, at high heat input fails from the interface.

M. Puranvari et al[25] studied the influence of heat input on microstructure and IMC layer thickness (reaction layer) during GTAW welding/brazing of dissimilar material Al 6061 to Zn coated steel. When heat input is less than 450 kJmm⁻¹, the thickness of IMC layer is smaller and holds poor joint strength. At the higher heat input 720 KJmm⁻¹, the IMC layer thickness is 3.9μm also produce high strength joint 210Nmm⁻². The strength is also dependent on first run (root run). It should be defect less.

Zhang et al[69] has reported that heat input rise from 613 Jcm⁻¹ and 961 Jcm⁻¹, also increases thickness of IMC layer 10μm to 40-50μm respectively and modifies its composition. Because of the presence of zinc, wettability was higher at low heat input than at high heat input.

B. Mezrag et al[70] studied the effect of current waveform on the metal transfer and heat transfer during dissimilar aluminum alloy to zinc coated steel joining with ER4043 filler wire by CMT process. They reported that boost phase duration of current waveform decreases with decrease in volume of liquid droplet at end of filler wire and also rises short-circuit frequency attributed to decrease in deposition rate and thickness of intermetallic layer at brazing interface.

5. Control of formation of IMC layer

Al-Si base filler wire assists in the reduction of IMC layer thickness due to the growth of FeAl and Fe-Al-Si compounds, which improves wettability, spreadability and mechanical properties of weld joint. Due to the addition of Si, the brittleness of the IMC layer is reduced by the ternary phase Fe-Al-Si. Fe-Al-Si slows diffusion and controls the growth of the Fe-Al binary phase. Al-Si5 and Al-Si12 (ER4043 and ER4047) are used for dissimilar Al to steel joining in automotive industry.

H. Dong et al[35] investigated the effect of different alloying element on strength and microstructure during joining of Aluminum alloy to GI steel Sheet by introducing different amount of Si, Cu, Zn into the weld through various filler wire viz. Al-Si5, Al-Si12, Al-Cu6, Al-Si10-Cu4 and Zn-Al15. Al-Si5, Al-Si12 suppress the growth of IMC layer with thickness 5 μ m and 2 μ m respectively due to diffusion of Fe from steel.

Conclusion

In this paper, approaches related to intermetallic layer formation during Al-steel dissimilar joining reported by various researchers. The growth of IMC layer majorly depends on heat input and process parameter such as current, voltage, speed, wfs etc. IMC layer thickness majorly depends on heat input. At the Aluminum to steel interface FeAl, Fe₃Al, Fe₂Al₅ and FeAl₃ compounds were formed and confirms the brittle IMC layer. Silicon base filler wire controls the growth kinetics of intermetallic compounds and thickness of IMC layer attributed to formation ternary phase Al-Fe-Si instead of Fe-Al binary phase.

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